

Bipositive Metal Complexes of Novel Schiff Bases derived from Carbazides and 2-Aminopyridine

(MFS.) PAPIA CHATTERJEE, (Miss) HARJIT KAUR DUGGAL, B. V. AGARWALA** and ARUN K. DEY*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Six Schiff base chelating ligands, viz. vanillin semicarbazone (VSC), 2-furaldehyde semicarbazone (FSC), vanillin thiosemicarbazone (VTSC), 2-furaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (FTSC), salicylaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (SAP) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (HNAP) and their complexes largely with bipositive cations are synthesised. The first four ligands exist in keto form but form complexes through deprotonated enolic form and the azomethine nitrogen to yield six-coordinated complexes with 2 moles of water are formed with VSC, FSC, Fe^{III}-VSC complex being ionic (molar conductance 71.2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$). The complexes formed by thiosemicarbazone analogues are four-coordinate and do not contain water molecules. Cu^{II}-VTSC, Cu^{II}-FTSC and Ni^{II}-VTSC are diamagnetic due to strong metal-metal interaction, giving rise to square-planar structures. The latter two bidentate ligands SAP and HNAP coordinate through azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen to yield octahedral complexes. Implication of magnetic, spectral and thermal data in relation to the different stereochemistry of the complexes are discussed.

SINCE the discovery of the first Schiff base salicylidene aniline and its methyl derivative¹, bidentate and multidentate Schiff bases have been synthesised²⁻⁶. They are characterised by the presence of C=N double bond and are excellent chelating ligands. The coordination chemistry of Schiff bases as acyclic polydentate ligands having delocalised π -orbitals gained importance for over two decades because of their use as models of biological systems⁶. The role of manganese(II) in its Schiff base complexes derived from salicylaldehyde and aliphatic amines are of significance in green plant photosynthesis⁷.

Among the Schiff bases, semicarbazones have been found to be useful as anticonvulsants⁸ and possess antipityviral activity⁹. Thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes show a wide spectrum of medicinal properties. They are active against tuberculosis, leprosy, rheumatism, bacterial and viral infections. They show antimalarial activity and such activities are often related to complexing abilities of these compounds with metal ions¹⁰⁻¹².

2-Aminopyridines and aromatic amines behave differently in the formation of Schiff bases¹⁴. Stereochemical features of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-(2'-aminoethyl)pyridine have been investigated¹⁵, which show subnormal magnetic moments due to the presence of exchange coupled antiferromagnetism. The hydrogen bonding and tautomeric equilibria in Schiff bases of 2-aminopyridine are illustrated by Ranganathan *et al.*¹⁵. Other studies include the eight-coordinate uranium complex with tetradentate Schiff base involving 2-amino-4-methylpyridine¹⁶ and heptadentate Schiff

base obtained from tris(2-aminoethyl)amine and three moles of salicylaldehyde. The latter forms a Fe^{III} complex in which the tertiary nitrogen atom of the amine is not bonded to Fe¹⁷ as revealed by X-ray studies. Moreover, Schiff base complexes also act as ligands to yield binuclear and bridged complexes^{18,19}. Their use as analytical reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions are also described^{20,21}.

In view of great interest involved in these compounds on account of their immense use in chemotherapy as well as a wide range of stereochemistries in complexation with metal ions, six Schiff bases have now been synthesised, viz. vanillin semicarbazone (VSC), 2-furaldehydesemicarbazone (FSC), vanillin thiosemicarbazone (VTSC), 2-furaldehyde (thiosemicarbazone) (FTSC), salicylaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (SAP) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (HNAP). The syntheses of iron(III) and several bipositive metal complexes are reported along with their characterisation by IR, DRS, thermal, magnetic and electrical conductance studies.

Experimental

Vanillin (4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde; Loba), 2-furaldehyde (Fluka), salicylaldehyde (S. Merck), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka, A.G.), semicarbazide hydrochloride (Loba), thiosemicarbazide (Loba), 2-aminopyridine (Merck) were used. Metal salts, solvents and physicochemical methods employed were the same as described earlier^{22,23}.

*Present address **Lawrenceganj, Allahabad-211 002. **Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, R. D. University, Jabalpur-482 001.

Synthesis of ligands :

Vanillin semicarbazone (VSC) and 2-furaldehyde semicarbazone (FSC) : Semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.1 mol, 11.5 g) was neutralised by adding 1 N NaOH (50 cm³). The mixture was heated to boiling, cooled and tested for neutrality by pH-paper. An ethanolic solution of 0.1 M vanillin (15.21 g) or 0.1 M 2-furaldehyde (8.2 cm³) was then slowly added to the above solution with continuous stirring. Both the mixtures were refluxed over a water-bath at ~100° for 2–3 h. Vanillin carbazone crystallised out on heating as a bright yellow mass. The crystals of 2-furaldehydesemicarbazone were obtained on standing the refluxed solution overnight and evaporating slightly. The semicarbazones were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure in a desiccator over silica gel. The products were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. : VSC, 230°; FSC, 188°.

Vanillin (VTSC) and 2-furaldehyde (FTSC) thiosemicarbazone : An ethanolic solution of 0.1 M vanillin or 0.1 M 2-furaldehyde was gradually added to an ethanolic solution of 0.1 M thiosemicarbazide (9.10 g) with vigorous shaking. Both the mixtures were then refluxed over a water-bath for 3–4 h and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting pale yellow fine needle like crystals separated out in the cases of VTSC and FTSC, were dried and recrystallised as above, m.p. : VTSC, 103°; FTSC, 148°.

Salicylaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (SAP) : Salicylaldehyde (5.23 cm³, 0.05 mol) was added gradually to the aminopyridine (4.70 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in ethanol with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. The ligand was prepared by evaporating the solvent to a small volume and cooling to room temperature, when it separated as crystals. The isolated yellow product was recrystallised with ethanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂, (70%), m.p. 74°.

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (HNAP) : To a solution of 2-aminopyridine (4.70 g, 0.05 mol) in ethanol was gradually added 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (8.60 g, 0.05 mol). The mixture was stirred and refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. On cooling, the resulting dark yellow solid was washed with alcohol and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂, (75%), m.p. 161°. The condensation reactions involved in the synthesis of ligands, their tautomeric forms and coordinating property are shown in Fig. 1.

Synthesis of metal complexes—VSC and FSC complexes : VSC (0.004 mol, 0.84 g) or FSC (0.004 mol, 0.65 g) in hot 1 : 1 ethanol–DMF (100 cm³) solvent mixture was refluxed with an aqueous solution of the metal salt (obtained by dissolving in minimum amount of water). Iron(III) chloride (0.002 mol, 0.33 g) or copper(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.40 g) was used. The resulting solid complex was washed with ethanol–DMF mixture followed by ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ under reduced pressure. The yield for Fe^{III}–

VSC complex was 0.84 g (83%), Cu–VSC complex 0.92 g (88%), Cu–FSC complex 0.80 g (98%). M.ps. of all the complexes were above 250°.

VTSC and FTSC complexes : A mixture of an alcoholic solution (100 cm³) of VTSC (0.9 g, 0.004 mol) and aqueous solution of the metal acetate (obtained by dissolving in minimum amount of water), viz. cobalt(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.49 g), nickel(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.49 g), copper(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.40 g), zinc(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.44 g) or cadmium(II) acetate (0.002 mol, 0.53 g), was refluxed for 3 h. Solid complexes of different colours were obtained depending upon the metal ions employed. The complexes were washed with ethanol followed by ether, and dried at room temperature. Yield of the complexes were, Co^{II} complex, 1.8 g (90%); Ni^{II} complex, 1.93 g (95%); Cu^{II} complex, 1.82 g (89%); Cd^{II} complex, 2.02 g (90%); and Zn^{II} complex, 1.96 g (95%). The complexes did not melt upto 250°.

Metal(II)–FTSC complexes were synthesised in an identical manner employing an ethanolic solution of FTSC (0.7 g, 0.004 mol) and an aqueous solution of the metal acetates (0.002 mol). The yield of the complexes were, Co^{II} complex, 0.80 g (78%); Ni^{II} complex, 0.78 g (77%); Cu^{II} complex, 0.80 g (80%); Zn^{II} complex, 0.83 g (82%); and Cd^{II} complex, 0.90 g (81%). All the complexes were stable upto 230°.

SAP and HNAP complexes : The complexes were synthesised by refluxing the metal salt solution (0.002 M) containing Mn(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O (0.50 g), Co(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O (0.50 g), Ni(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O (0.50 g) or Cu(CH₃COO)₂·H₂O (0.40 g) with ethanolic solution (0.004 M) of SAP (0.792 g) or HNAP (0.992 g). The mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h on a water-bath. In case of SAP, complexes were isolated by adding liquor ammonia (4–5 drops) and refluxing further for 2 h. The complexes thus isolated were collected on a sintered funnel, washed with ethanol and treated in the similar manner as above. The yields were ~80% in each case.

Results and Discussion

Characterisation of the ligands : The compositions of the six ligands VSC, FSC, VTSC, FTSC, SAP and HNAP, as determined by microanalytical method (Table 1) reveal that the aldehydes react with thiosemicarbazide and 2-aminopyridine in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

The ir spectra of VSC and VTSC exhibit characteristic bands in the region ~3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH) due to the presence of *para*-substituted OH group in vanillin. Both the ligands show characteristic bands at 3 500 cm⁻¹ (NH)²⁴. The bands at 1 680–1 670 cm⁻¹ are indicative of C=O stretching. The C=O in-plane and out-of-plane deformations²⁵ are observed at 670 and 610 cm⁻¹. The band at 1 500 cm⁻¹ in FSC and FTSC is assigned to the stretching

Fig. 1. Condensation reaction, tautomeric form and position of donor atoms—Schiff base ligands.

vibration of furan oxygen. The band at 1550 cm^{-1} , (N—C—N)²⁷ suggests that the ligand exists in its thione form as represented by the structure (Fig. 1, a, b) in the solid state. Intense bands observed at 1460 (C=S)^{28} and 820 cm^{-1} (NH—C=S)²⁹ support the above observation.

In the case of SAP and HNAP, broad bands are observed at $3000-3100$ and $2920-3060\text{ cm}^{-1}$

which may tentatively be assigned to intramolecular hydrogen bonding^{30,31}. Similar findings in respect of the OH frequency have been reported by Martin³² who showed that salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone exhibit broad weak OH bands at $2900-2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Investigations by Colleter³³ and Williams and Fleming³⁴ also support our proposition, however, lower frequencies are also

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Elemental Analyses % :			
		(Found/Calcd.)			
		Metal	O	H	N
HL ¹	Bright yellow	—	51.6	5.1	19.8
[FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ^a	Chocolate brown	9.8 (10.2)	40.4 (39.1)	4.4 (4.4)	15.7 (15.4)
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Dark brown	10.8 (12.8)	42.5 (42.0)	4.8 (4.6)	16.0 (16.3)
HL ²	Pale yellow	—	48.2 (47.0)	4.8 (4.5)	28.0 (27.4)
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	15.0 (15.7)	35.0 (35.6)	3.9 (3.9)	20.0 (20.8)
HL ³	Pale yellow	—	48.0 (47.7)	4.8 (4.2)	18.6 (17.5)
[CoL ₂]	Shiny black	11.0 (11.6)	40.2 (42.6)	3.8 (3.9)	16.0 (16.5)
[NiL ₂]	Shiny black	10.8 (11.5)	41.4 (42.6)	4.3 (3.9)	15.9 (16.5)
[CuL ₂]	Greenish yellow	11.2 (12.4)	42.2 (42.2)	4.0 (3.9)	14.9 (16.4)
[ZnL ₂]	White	12.0 (12.7)	41.2 (42.0)	4.0 (3.9)	15.0 (16.3)
[CdL ₂]	Light yellow	18.9 (20.0)	37.5 (38.5)	3.8 (3.5)	14.0 (14.9)
HL ⁴	Pale yellow	—	42.2 (42.6)	4.3 (4.1)	23.9 (24.8)
[CoL ₂]	Shiny purple	13.6 (14.8)	36.8 (36.5)	3.5 (3.0)	20.4 (21.3)
[NiL ₂]	Shiny black	13.5 (14.8)	36.1 (36.5)	3.1 (3.0)	20.7 (21.3)
[CuL ₂]	Brown	15.0 (15.3)	36.4 (36.0)	3.2 (3.0)	20.4 (21.0)
[ZnL ₂]	Dirty white	15.5 (16.3)	35.0 (35.8)	3.9 (3.0)	21.0 (20.9)
[CdL ₂]	Yellow	23.0 (25.0)	30.8 (32.1)	3.0 (2.7)	17.8 (18.7)
HL ⁵	Yellow	—	72.7 (72.7)	5.2 (5.0)	14.5 (14.1)
[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	11.2 (11.3)	59.2 (59.3)	4.4 (4.5)	11.5 (11.5)
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Green	12.0 (12.0)	58.9 (58.9)	4.5 (4.4)	11.4 (11.4)
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	12.7 (12.8)	58.4 (58.3)	4.4 (4.4)	11.5 (11.3)
HL ⁶	Dark yellow	—	77.2 (77.4)	4.8 (4.8)	11.2 (11.2)
[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Orange	9.3 (9.8)	65.8 (65.6)	4.3 (4.4)	9.6 (9.5)
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	10.0 (10.0)	65.6 (65.2)	4.3 (4.4)	9.5 (9.5)
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish green	9.9 (9.9)	65.3 (65.2)	4.4 (4.4)	9.4 (9.5)
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Greenish brown	10.5 (10.7)	64.9 (64.6)	4.2 (4.3)	9.4 (9.4)

*HL¹=Vanillin semicarbazone (VSC), HL²=2-furaldehyde semicarbazone (FSC), HL³=vanillin thiosemicarbazone (VTSC), HL⁴=2-furaldehydethiosemicarbazone (FTSC), HL⁵=salicylaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (SAP), HL⁶=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-2-aminopyridine (HNAP). ^aFound: 7.0. Calcd.: 6.5%.

reported. The band at 1580–1635 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in all the six ligands indicate that aldehydes have condensed together with carbazone, thiosemicarbazone or aminopyridine^{25,26}. The spectral data of the ligands are summarised in Table 2.

Characterisation of complexes: The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) indicate that they have 1 : 2 stoichiometry having the general formula [ML₂(H₂O)₂], (HL¹⁻⁴=VSC, FSC, SAP or

 TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF LIGANDS

Band	VSC	FSC	VTSC	FTSC	SAP	HNAP
ν_{O-H}	3500	—	3500	—	3000–3100	2920–3060
ν_{NH}	3300, 3030	3310, 3020	3400	3500	—	—
$\nu_{Furan-O}$	—	1510	—	1500	—	—
$\nu_{C=S}/\nu_{C=O}$	1680	1680	1460	1450	—	—
$\nu_{NH-C=S}$	—	—	1320	1330	—	—
ν_{N-N}	1020	1010	1050	1030	—	—
$\nu_{C=N}$	1635	1640	1640	1650	1580	1580
ν_{OCH_2}	2840	—	2840	—	—	—

HNAP), ML^{5,6} (HL=VTSC, FTSC), where M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}. The iron(III) complex is formulated as [FeL₂(H₂O)₂]Cl and checked by ir, thermogravimetric and electrical conductance studies. The molar conductivity of Fe^{III}-VSC complex (71.2 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) suggests 1 : 1 electrolytic nature confirming the presence of ionic chlorine (Table 1).

Infrared spectra: The C=O stretching band observed in VSC, FSC at 1680 cm⁻¹ is not present in their complexes and instead new bands appear at 1340–1345 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu_{N-C=O}$. This shows enolisation of the keto groups and their subsequent deprotonation during complex formation²⁷ (Table 3). The deprotonation is further confirmed by the appearance of a new band at 1565–1550 cm⁻¹ (C=N–N=C). This suggests that the amide oxygen is bonded in enolic form upon deprotonation²⁸ in each case. The enolisation is enhanced due to stabilisation of the anion by conjugation with C=N–N=C²⁹. Similar observations are made for the corresponding sulphur ligand analog VTSC and FTSC where a band due to ν_{C-S} present in the ligands disappears on complex formation and new bands appear at 1600–1560 cm⁻¹ (C=N–N=C) and 700–670 cm⁻¹ (C–S)⁴⁰. This observation is in concurrence with thioenolisation

of the $-NH-\overset{|}{C}=S$ group of the ligands to $-\overset{|}{N}=\overset{|}{C}-SH$ in solution which occurs on complexation with metal ions⁴¹.

All the six ligands show a strong band at 1520–1645 cm⁻¹ (C=N)⁴², and on complexation a negative shift by ~20–60 cm⁻¹ is observed in each case, emphasising participation of the azomethine nitrogen in coordination⁴³⁻⁴⁶. Incidentally, downward shift in ν_{C-N} indicating positive involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination has been observed by a large number of investigators. A positive shift of 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the stretching frequency of N–N moiety in the spectra of the complexes further supports the coordination of metal atom through the azomethine nitrogen⁴⁷. The coordination through azomethine nitrogen and enolic oxygen/sulphur is further substantiated by the appearance of additional ν_{M-N} ⁴⁸ and ν_{M-O}/ν_{M-S} ^{49,50} in the metal sensitive region.

TABLE 3—IMPORTANT IR SPECTRAL BAND (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES

Band	Metal complexes with					
	VTSC	FTSC	VSC	FSC	SAP	HNAP
ν_{OH}	3 500–3 550	—	3 400–3 450	3 450	—	—
ν_{NH}	—	—	3 300	3 290	—	—
$\nu_{C=N}$	1 610–1 630	1 600–1 620	1 610–1 615	1 610	1 520–1 525	1 520–1 540
$\nu_{C=N-N=C}$	1 560–1 590	1 560–1 600	1 570–1 580	1 565	—	—
ν_{N-N}	1 020–1 045	1 040–1 050	1 030	1 025	—	—
ν_{C-S}	650–700	620–680	—	—	—	—
ν_{M-N}	460–480	450–480	550–570	550	460–475	450
ν_{M-S}	290–310	260–280	—	—	—	—
ν_{M-O}	—	—	590–600	600	580–590	560–650
δ_{H_2O}	—	—	1 640	1 635	1 610–1 620	1 605–1 620
γ_{H_2O}	—	—	760–770	780	730–745	725–740

Newer bands in all the complexes (except of VTSC, FTSC) have been observed due to deformation (1 605–1 640 cm⁻¹) and rocking modes (725–780 cm⁻¹) of coordinated water^{51,52}. Complexes formed by VTSC, FTSC, however, do not show any such band assignable to coordinated water.

Magnetic measurements: The mean value of gram susceptibility determined at 5, 10, 15 A current denoted as χ_{g1} , χ_{g2} and χ_{g3} was subjected to diamagnetic correction. The magnetic moments of the six Schiff base complexes are given in Table 4. The magnetic moment value of Fe^{III}–VSC complex is found to be 5.90 B.M. indicating it to be high-spin type paramagnetic. It lies within the octahedral range 5.3–5.9 B.M. and thus supports octahedral stereochemistry⁵⁵. Gullotti *et al.*⁵⁴ reported the values of 5.7–6.0 B.M. for the optically active monomeric complexes formed by iron(III) with quadridentate Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde. The copper(II) complexes of VSC and FSC exhibit magnetic moment values of 1.77 and 1.72 B.M. respectively at room temperature, which lie well within the range 1.71–2.20 B.M. for octahedral geometry in copper(II) complexes⁵⁶.

For tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes ⁴T₁ and ⁴T₂ states are mixed into the ground state under the action of the spin-orbit coupling and $\mu_{eff} = 2 \left(-1 - 4 \frac{\lambda}{10Dq} \right) [S(S+1)]^{1/2}$ B.M. The experi-

mental value, as reported in literature lies in the range 4.4–4.7 B.M. The magnetic moments for the VTSC and FTSC complexes are 4.43 and 4.30 B.M. respectively, which lie well within the range for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁵⁷. In the case of tetrahedral Ni^{II} ion a large orbital contribution is expected as the ground state T₁ is essentially (e_g⁴t_{2g}⁴). This accounts for the magnetic moment value to be expected ~4.0 B.M. as compared to octahedral complexes which have magnetic moment of 3.33 B.M.⁵⁸ or less as the ground state ³A_{1g} cannot be crossed by any singlet level. This results in paramagnetism of octahedral nickel(II). An inverse relation between the magnitude of the moment and distortion of nickel(II) complexes from the tetrahedral geometry has also been suggested⁵⁹. The nickel(II) complexes of VTSC and FTSC are found to be diamagnetic, which suggests that they have square-planar configuration. The diamagnetism of the nickel(II) complexes is a strong evidence that coordination occurs through thiol sulphur atom since thiols can cause spin-pairing in the complexes⁶⁰.

TABLE 4—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY MEASUREMENT AT 0, 5, 10, AND 15 A

Compd.	χ_{g1} × 10 ⁻⁶	χ_{g2} × 10 ⁻⁶	χ_{g3} × 10 ⁻⁶	Mean of		μ_{eff} B.M.
				χ_{g1} , χ_{g2} , χ_{g3} × 10 ⁻⁶	$\chi_{M/}$ × 10 ⁻⁶	
[FeL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	20.0	29.0	28.7	25.9	14 348	5.90
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	2.12	2.3	2.0	2.1	1 296	1.77
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1.6	3.6	2.9	2.7	1 219	1.72
[CoL ₂]	10.0	14.9	9.9	11.6	8 109	4.43
[NiL ₂]						0
[CuL ₂]						0
[CoL ₂]	14.9	17.8	23.9	18.8	7 565	4.30
[NiL ₂]						0
[CuL ₂]	2.8	3.6	2.6	3.0	1 342	1.81
[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	27.1	29.8	32.0	29.6	14 354	5.94
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	19.6	23.0	17.1	19.9	9 730	4.91
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1.4	4.0	2.2	2.5	1 234	1.86
[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	24.1	25.7	25.3	25.0	14 624	6.00
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	16.6	17.3	14.7	16.2	9 541	4.87
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	6.2	6.2	5.5	6.0	3 532	3.02
[CuL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1.5	2.6	2.4	2.2	1 306	1.93

The magnetic moments of simple copper(II) complexes generally occur in the range 1.75–2.20 B.M. irrespective of the stereochemistry involved and is independent of temperature in most of the monomeric complexes, except for extremely low temperatures (<5 K). The copper(II) complex of VTSC is also found to be diamagnetic which indicates strong metal-metal interaction^{61,62} giving rise to square-planar structure. Copper forms many complexes in which Cu–Cu distances are short enough to indicate significant M–M interactions but in no case actual Cu–Cu bonds are present⁶³. Attempts to specify the detailed nature of this interaction have been plagued by controversy and there are still considerable difference of opinion about its precise nature⁶⁴. Melkin⁶⁵ interpreted antiferromagnetic exchange between coupled pairs of Cu

atoms. Subnormal magnetic moments of copper complexes have been reported by several investigators^{6,67} and are presumed to be attributable to super-exchange phenomenon as metal-metal interaction in a dimer structure, arising from the molecular association of the complexes. On the other hand, the Cu^{II}-FTSC complex is paramagnetic and the magnetic moment is 1.81 B.M., indicating that the orbital contribution is almost quenched by the crystal field⁶⁸ and the complex has a square-planar configuration⁶⁹⁻⁷¹. The values of magnetic moments of the SAP and HNAP complexes and detailed observations of magnetic susceptibility measurements have been incorporated in Table 4. The zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes formed by VTSC and FTSC are diamagnetic as expected.

Diffuse reflectance spectra :

Octahedral complexes : The reflectance spectra of the Fe^{III}-VSC complex show four weak bands in the region 18 607-30 303 cm⁻¹. In a weak octahedral field the ground state of iron(III), ⁶A_{1g} has one electron in each *d*-orbital making it high-spin type. In complexes of a *d*⁵ system, there are no spin-allowed *d-d* transitions. All are both spin- and Laporte-forbidden. An aid in making band assignments results from the fact that the spin-forbidden transitions are usually sharp⁷². The bands observed in the reflectance spectra of the iron(III) complex are weak and may be assigned to spin-forbidden transitions under octahedral stereochemistry which is supported by the observed room temperature μ_{eff} value (5.90 B.M.) and together with the magnetic moment value, the complex may be assigned an octahedral symmetry⁷³.

The spectra of several copper(II) complexes in an octahedral environment have been extensively studied⁷⁴. The Cu^{II}-VSC complex shows a broad band enveloped around 15 384 cm⁻¹ due to ²T_{2g} ← ³E_g transition in the octahedral field⁷⁵. The broadening of the band is due to Jahn-Teller effect resulting from the unequal occupation of e_g orbitals. The Cu^{II}-FSC complex exhibits only one broad band centred around 14 500 cm⁻¹, suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry for the complex⁷⁶.

High energy transition bands occur at 30 769 and 25 000 cm⁻¹ in the Cu^{II}-VSC and Cu^{II}-FSC respectively and may be assigned to charge transfer or intra-ligand transitions^{77,78}. No absorption band is observed below 10 000 cm⁻¹ in any

copper(II) complex which rules out the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral geometry. The copper(II) complexes of SAP and HNAP are also octahedral which is supported by σ_1/σ_2 values (1.08). Band positions and ligand field parameters of other complexes are shown in Table 5.

Tetrahedral/square-planar complexes : The cobalt(II) complex has a quartet ground state and three spin-allowed transitions are possible to the excited quartet states. Since most of the planar complexes are of low-spin type, tetrahedral geometry could be expected for the Co^{II}-VTSC and Co^{II}-FTSC complexes. This is supported by their room temperature magnetic moments which are found to be 4.6 and 4.3 B.M. respectively and are well within the range of tetrahedral configuration. From the energy level diagram (Fig. 2) for tetrahedral *d*⁷ configuration it is obvious that such a system should exhibit three transitions arising from ground state ⁴A_{2g} to higher excited states. As ν_1 is rarely observed and the band corresponding to ν_2 transition, ⁴T_{1g}(F) ← ⁴A_{2g} is usually broad, but ν_3 = ⁴T_{1g}(P)

Fig. 2. Energy level diagram for tetrahedral *d*⁷-configuration.

← ⁴A_{2g} transition is quite intense, broad and exhibits an important role in structural characterisation⁷⁹. The Co^{II}-VTSC and Co^{II}-FTSC complexes exhibit two bands near 16 666, 19 230 and 16 129, 18 181 cm⁻¹ respectively which correspond to transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F) ← ⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(P) ← ⁴A_{2g}(F) in a tetrahedral field⁷⁹.

Square-planar nickel(II) complexes show one transition band assigned to ¹B_{1g} → ¹A_{1g}⁸⁰. Both the Ni^{II}-VTSC and Ni^{II}-FTSC complexes exhibit only one transition band each at 20 000 and 21 276 cm⁻¹ respectively. Both the complexes are diamagnetic which suggests square-planar structure. The higher energy bands of Ni^{II} ion have been

TABLE 5—BAND POSITION AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Band position cm ⁻¹	10 Dq	B'	β	β ⁰	ν_2 cm ⁻¹	ν_2/ν_1
Co ^{II} -SAP	11 363, 23 809	11 363	829.5	0.854	14.57	22 726	2.0
Cu ^{II} -SAP	13 888, 12 820, 10 869	4 720.33	—	—	—	—	—
Co ^{II} -HNAP	11 111, 23 809	12 510	939.8	0.967	3.21	23 621	2.1
Ni ^{II} -HNAP	10 638, 18 518, 27 027	10 638	797.5	0.755	24.47	18 518	1.7
Cu ^{II} -HNAP	13 888	6 534.42	—	—	—	—	—

apparently submerged due to charge transfer and intra-ligand transitions.

The spectra of the Cu^{II} -VTSC complex exhibit a band at $15\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is in agreement with the reported value for Cu^{II} ion in square-planar environment⁸¹⁻⁸³. The band may be attributed to the transition ${}^3E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ allowed for the d^9 Cu^{II} ion in the complex indicating a square-planar geometry. The diamagnetic behaviour coupled with the reflectance spectra helps to assume a dimeric structure for the Cu^{II} -VTSC complex involving dsp^2 hybridisation. The reflectance spectra of the other copper(II) complex formed by FTSC also show one characteristic absorption maxima at $14\,050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and may be assigned the above geometry^{84,85}.

Thermogravimetry :

TG data of the semicarbazone complexes, viz. Fe^{III} -VSC, Cu^{II} -VSC and Cu^{II} -FSC show that they lose weight between 100 and 250° , the weight loss corresponding to the presence of two coordinated water molecules. The Fe^{III} -VSC complex shows a 6.41% loss in weight (theor. 6.5%) and the Cu^{II} -VSC complex 7.6% (theor. 7.0%) equivalent to the elimination of $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The decomposition temperatures denote that the Fe^{III} -VSC complex breaks up at 250° , Cu^{II} -VSC at 280° and Cu^{II} -FSC at 360° . Thus, the order of thermal stability of the complexes are Fe^{III} -VSC $<$ Cu^{II} -VSC $<$ Cu^{II} -FSC. The final residues obtained in the case of the Fe^{III} -VSC, Cu^{II} -VSC and Cu^{II} -FSC complexes were found to correspond to their respective metal oxides (Fe_2O_3 , CuO). A similar trend is observed in the thermograms of SAP and HNAP complexes.

The VTSC complexes formed by bipovalent cations remain stable upto 240 – 280° and later decompose rapidly leaving a stable residue in the case of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} . Only the cadmium(II) complex does not form any stable residue and the decomposition continues beyond 800° . Thermal stabilities of the complexes is found to follow the order, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. Thermograms of the FTSC complexes show a striking feature as none of the complexes (except Zn^{II}) forms a stable compound at the end, showing that the decomposition continues beyond 800° . The thermal stabilities of the complexes follow the order, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$.

By studying magnetic moments, thermogravimetry, ir and diffuse reflectance spectra, the structures of the complexes have been tentatively elucidated. The complexation occurs through deprotonated enolic form of the semicarbazone and its azomethine nitrogen to yield six-coordinated complexes with two moles of water. The presence of chlorine in ionic Fe^{III} -VSC complexes is indicated. The complexes formed by thiosemicarbazone analogs are four-coordinate and do not contain any water molecules. Other two bidentate Schiff base ligands SAP and HNAP coordinate through azomethine

nitrogen and phenolic oxygen to yield octahedral complexes. The coordination positions of all the six Schiff base ligands are shown in Fig. 1.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. H. SCHIFF, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1864, 131, 118.
2. G. WILKINSON, R. D. GILLARD and J. A. MCOLIVER, "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", Pergamon, New York, 1987, Vol. 2.
3. T. MATSUSHITA and T. SHONO, *Polyhedron*, 1986, 5, 785.
4. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 19, 5.
5. P. L. MAURYA, C. P. DUBE and B. V. AGARWALA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 1400.
6. M. GULLOTI, L. CASSELLA, A. PASINI and R. UGO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 339.
7. R. L. HEATH, *Int. Rev. Cytol.*, 1973, 34, 44.
8. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, E. MORRISON and Y. ROGERS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, 127, L17.
9. G. SCHUSTER, L. HEINISCH, W. SCHULZE, H. ULBRICH and H. WILLITZER, *Phytopathology*, 1984, 97, 2.
10. S. PADHYE and G. B. KAUFFMAN, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1985, 63, 127.
11. T. M. BAMGBOYE and O. A. BAMGBOYE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, 133, 245.
12. C. F. BELL, K. A. K. LOTT and N. HEARN, *Polyhedron*, 1987, 6, 39.
13. A. EL DISSOUKY, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1987, 43, 1177.
14. H. RANGANATHAN, T. RAMASWAMI, D. RAMASWAMY and M. SANTAPPA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1979, 1201; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 127.
15. D. K. RASTOGI and P. C. PACHAURI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 151.
16. H. N. MEHROTRA and K. C. DASH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organic Chem.*, 1978, 8, 48.
17. D. F. COOK, D. CUMMINS and E. D. MCKENZIE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 1869.
18. E. SINN and C. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 4, 391.
19. K. KASUGA, T. NAGAHARA and Y. YAMAMOTO, *Polyhedron*, 1985, 4, 415.
20. M. BONILLA-ALVAREZ, M. PALMERI, D. DAVIS and J. S. FRITZ, *Talanta*, 1987, 34, 473.
21. M. ROY, M. Phil. Dissertation, Jabalpur University, 1987.
22. A. K. DRY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 857.
23. D. K. DWIVEDI, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DRY, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belg.*, 1987, 96, 431; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 461.
24. K. L. REDDY, S. SRIHARI and P. LINGAIAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 318.
25. M. NONOYAMA, S. TOMITA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 12, 33.
26. T. MIYAZAWA, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1960, 4, 155, 168.
27. R. C. STAUFER and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 806.
28. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, 38, 646.
29. E. LIEBER, C. N. R. RAO, C. N. FILLAI, J. RAMACHANDRAN and R. D. HITES, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1958, 36, 801.
30. L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
31. J. R. DYER, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New Jersey.
32. MARTIN, *Nature (London)*, 1960, 166, 74; Ref. 30.
33. J. C. COLLECTER, *Ann. Chim.*, 1960, 5, 415.
34. D. H. WILLIAMS and I. FLEMING, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, 1980, pp. 67, 49.

85. N. K. DUTTA and N. C. CHAKDER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 2809.
86. L. D. FREDRIKSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 1849.
87. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and E. S. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1975.
88. A. SYAMAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 179.
89. A. SYAMAL and M. R. MAURYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 886.
90. M. D. ALI and R. BOSE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 265.
91. H. K. REDDY and D. V. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 154.
92. X. W. DOUGLAS, R. M. MAKEEVER, J. P. SCOVILL and D. L. KLAYMAN, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 947.
93. A. BRAIBANTI, F. DALLAWASILE, M. A. PELLINGHELI and E. LEAFORATI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1430.
94. B. D. SHARMA and J. C. BAILER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5476.
95. R. CEVALU, R. BOSCO, F. BONATI, F. MAGGIO and R. BARBIERI *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1970, **376**, 180.
96. F. MAGGIO, T. PIZZINO, V. ROMANO and G. DIA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1478.
97. N. RAMA RAO, T. V. J. VENKATESWARA RAO and M. C. GANORKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 877.
98. R. A. CONDRATE and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 2590.
99. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970, pp. 107, 159, 241.
100. V. J. TYAGARAJU, V. RANBAORE, V. ATRÉ and M. C. GANORKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 199.
101. F. FUJITA, K. NAKAMOTO and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3963.
102. A. R. NICHOLSON and G. J. SUTTON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 373.
103. T. MIYAZAWA, T. SHIMANOUCI and S. MIZUSHIMA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 408, 1958, **29**, 611.
104. M. GULLOTTI, L. CASSELLA, A. PASINI and R. UGO, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 339.
105. S. A. COTTON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 187.
106. T. R. RAO, N. SAHAY and R. O. AGGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 79.
107. F. A. COTTON and M. GOODGAME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
108. H. RANGANATHAN, T. RAMASWAMY, D. RAMASWAMY and M. SANTAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 127.
109. R. S. NYHOLM, *Chem. Rev.*, 1959, **53**, 263.
110. S. E. LIVINGSTONE *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, **19**, 386.
111. S. YAMADA, N. NISHIKAWA and T. TSUCHIDO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1960, **33**, 1278.
112. B. V. AGARWALA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **36**, 209.
113. M. KATO, H. O. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 99.
114. A. F. HANSEN and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 681.
115. A. MELKIN, *Polyhedron*, 1982, **1**, 143.
116. P. W. BALL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **4**, 361.
117. A. D. GINSBERG, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1971, **5**, 45.
118. W. E. HATFIELD and Y. MUTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 97.
119. M. A. ALI and M. T. H. TARAFDER *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1785.
120. M. A. ALI and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **13**, 101.
121. M. T. H. TARAFDER, B. MONOWARA and M. L. RAHMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 337.
122. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", East-West Edition, New Delhi, 1978, p. 162.
123. J. A. BORTRAD and D. G. ELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 927.
124. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1976, p. 916.
125. R. NEIMAN and D. KIVELSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
126. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 357.
127. Y. NISHIDA and S. KIDA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **27**, 275.
128. L. F. LARKUORTHY and K. C. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1263.
129. R. O. KULBE, V. K. BHOON and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 194.
130. M. A. ALI and R. N. BOSE, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 522.
131. I. M. PROCTOR, B. J. HATHAWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1678.
132. B. C. WERDEN, E. BILLING and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 97.
133. C. M. HARRIS, E. F. HOSKIN and R. L. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3728.
134. J. BJERRUM, C. J. BALLHAUSEN and C. K. JØRGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 1275.
135. L. E. ORGEL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **23**, 6.